

**WOMEN IN EDUCATION AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN ORON
FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Education plays great role in empowering women to contribute to development, but the barriers of culture of exclusion driven by ideologies of patriarchy has brought about the slow pace in attaining development in many communities across Africa. This descriptive research sought to examine the roles of education in empowering women to contribute to the development of Oron Federal Constituency of Akwa Ibom State. Women in Development Theory (WID) was adopted as theoretical guide. A total of 393 study participant were engaged as sample size from the 5 local government areas of the constituency. Both primary and secondary data were analysed by the researcher. Primary data were gathered through the use of questionnaire and were analysed descriptively using of frequency tables. Findings of the study shown that more female pupils are enrolled in the 107 primary school which implies high level of female education, women engage in various programmes like educational intervention, health care intervention, community development levy toward the development of the constituency, and factors like cultural belief, poverty, family roles and early marriage constitute barriers to women participation in development. Based on these findings, the researchers among others recommended that cultural practice of women exclusion should be abolished among the people of Oron Federal Constituency and Akwa Ibom State as a whole.

KEYWORDS: Education, development, women, culture and Oron

INTRODUCTION

Education is fundamental to the development of the human capacity (Bassey, 2016). Within the National Policy on Education, there is provision for equal opportunities (equalitarianism) for males and females in schools and even in adult education (of men and women) that is not within the formal school system. Thus the National Policy on Education recognizes equality of men and women when it comes to education (Benjamin, 2008). This policy has created the right for the girl child building on the United Nations General Assembly in its 57th meeting in December 2002, which proclaimed 2005-2014 as United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (Benjamin, 2008). According to Sharma (2016), education for Sustainable Development emphasizes education of all to be an indispensable element for achieving sustainable development. This act recognized the capacity of educated women in contributing to community development worldwide.

Samuel (2016) argued that community development is one of the alternative vehicles for the positive transformation of societies. This in its implication ascertains the fact every city, town and urban centre is driven through the base of community development by people participation in the developmental programmes of such place. The United Nations in 1956 defined community development as a “process by which the efforts of the people are united with those of governmental authorities to improve the economic, social and cultural conditions of communities, to integrate these communities into the life of the nation and enable them to contribute fully to the national progress” (UN, 2019). Mere (1982) in his work “*Economic for a Developing World*” also accentuated that community development is an instrument of social advancement of all communities (Samuel, 2016). Community developments especially among the developing nations have taken centre stage of concern for every organization within and outside the developing nations. The quest for sustainable development goals is to attain great success in community development by meeting the various classes of human needs especially in the third world. Every definition of community development will advocates the advancement of human lives and socio-economic statuses within any given community, but one of the key factor that have been proven to contribute to the achieving development from community perspective remains education. With the population of girls being born into our society everyday, and the mark set by the educated women in their various contributions toward the development of their respective community, girl child education seem to be calling for more and more policy, investment, and provisions for its growth especially in Africa.

Women's education is very important for the development of our communities, states, nations, and key to the achievement of global sustainable development. Due to the rising population of women in our society, educating our women is giving empowerment to a good percentage of our population to contribute their quota to the development of our families, communities, state, and nation at large. According to Alan (2010), sustainable development of any country depends on the full and equal participation of women and men, education brings about empowerment and in other words; education empowers women to engage in sustainable development activities. Benjamin (2008) posits that, today most of the educated men desire to marry educated women, so that their children will have educated mothers, and this marks a great change in male attitude to the education of women and a steadily increasing demand for girls' education. The results of these educated women are gradually influencing the Nigerian society and are changing the views of women and other as such influence is steadily changing

the old-fashioned attitudes (Benjamin, 2008). According to Somani (2017), girls' education is pivotal to the development of society. This is given credence by the saying of Greg Mortenson; "If you teach a boy, you educate an individual; but if you teach a girl, you educate a community."

According to Sharma (2016), women play important and varied roles from home to society to workplace as a homemaker, societal wellbeing and job provider and job seeker respectively. Fortunate African women who enjoyed good education have proven their abilities in several walks of life (Benjamin, 2008). They are found among successfully doctors, teachers, lawyers, and are found in industry, commerce and public administration. These set of women have proved the case for women's education by demonstrating their usefulness outside the home (Benjamin, 2008). Sharma (2016) posits that women are visible backbone of any civilized society in the role of friend, daughter, daughter-in-law, sister, wife, mother or a role of working woman; women have facilitated this male dominant society in every aspect, and constitute approximately 50% of the World's population.

According to Osirike, and Egbayabo, (2012), community development is a derivation of two main concepts: community organization and economic development. Osirike, and Egbayabo, (2012) also argued that although defined in varying ways, community development implies mutually related development activities and situations. It is geared towards solving the problems of the community in order to raise their standard of living as well as promoting social welfare and development. The process of community development involves various activities ranging from tackling of specific tasks on aspects of community welfare to multipurpose programmes aimed at the transformation of the social organization and values of the whole community

Currently, women have risen to a higher profile in community development projects and likewise in decision making processes in the area. Their involvement was due to the fact that, some of the cultural values, beliefs and practices that determined the position of women in the past, have undergone drastic restructuring while others have been completely rendered obsolete. At the same time, new roles and values have also emerged (Osirike, and Egbayabo, 2012). From this lay down perspectives, this research work seeks to concentrate on the roles of education in empowering women in Oron Federal Constituency, Akwa Ibom State to contribute to their community development at different levels, through various developmental programmes.

Culture of exclusion of women in decision making, in a patriarchal society is posing great barrier to the pace at which sustainable development through execution of community development programmes should be achieved. British Council (2012) argued that many diverse socio-cultural factors influence the value that parents attach to their daughters' education. Gender norms and stereotypes exclude women and girls from decision-making, community participation and control over their own lives in many areas. Women as wives, mothers and caregivers understand the weight of various challenges facing the human world. This is because, they have been at the receiving ends of these social, economic, political, leadership, and war crisis. As a response to these issues, educated women have the capacity to contribute to development programmes which can alleviate the root causes of some of these problems.

Most of the educated women today are considered, rated and treated as weaker vessels

because of the cultural doctrine associated with women treatment. This has forced some educated men, who have received same level of education with this class of women to put up restriction in opportunities for educated women to participate in community leadership, thereby preventing educated women participation in community development decision making. Though, more educated women are rising up today to take up challenges that are facing their families, communities and nation at large. The exclusion of educated women in community decision making due to cultural norm and traditions is hampering the pace at which women participation in community development programmes would have attained success in our various community, state, and by extension the nation Sharma (2016).

As women education is rising in influence in our society every day, the number of girl child in educational institutions is increasing, and our society is having more educated women who are mentally empowered to contribute their own quota at homes and communities. The rising number of educated women in our society has reduced many of our social problems like in increasing the number of women going for antenatal, increasing the number of nursing mothers going for immunization of their children, increasing the number of working women in different fields of professions. These educated women have contributed to reduction of poverty at family levels and in empowering others within their reach. According to Peters, Bassey and Usoro (2019), educating girls is a particularly effective way of eradicating poverty and the positive effects of education for girls are well documented on the health and welfare of families as well as on economic opportunities and social transformation on a larger scale. Social responsibility burden at individual and family levels of most men have been greatly reduced by the roles of educated women who are their wives, relatives or partners. The rising numbers of educated women have been more of advantage for many families today to the extent that it is reducing the cultural norm of and problems associated with having only female children in a patriarchal society.

In Oron Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom State, women education is on the same level of policy implementation, resource investment, free and compulsory at the primary and secondary levels. Educated women in Oron Federal Constituency are increasing in number. They have set many stride in their quest to contribute to alleviation of social, economic, political, leadership, family, and community problems. The Present deputy governor of Akwa Ibom State Senator Akon Ekaenyi is an icon of the subject. Their set marks in the community development speak for the importance of girl child education, but the challenge of overcoming the cultural norms associated with women restrictions in accordance to various traditional practices found within the cultural and ideological diversity of the people of Oron Federal Constituency still call for concern, as in lifting the culture bars for effective women participation in community development. Literatures like Benjamin (2008) and Sharma (2016) present the fortunes, privileges, occupations, contributions to works and families of educated women, but the roles of the educated women in community development is the identified gap which this research work sought to fill. On this backdrop, this research work seeks to fill this gap in the literature, by examining the roles of education in enhancing women participation in community development in Oron Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Women In Development Theory “WID”

“Women in Development” (WID) theory has its root in Ester Boserup work of 1970. According to Colombo in Commission of the European Communities of 1984, since the Danish economist Ester Boserup published *Women's Role in Economic Development* in 1970, it gradually has become clear that not only is there a women's issue in most Third World countries - since their structure is often founded on a concept of the inferiority of women and a denial of their right to active participation in social life - but there is also a women's issue characteristic of these countries. In other words, under-development has specific and particularly grave implications for the status of women, implications that are being accentuated rather than mitigated by the process of modernization and development.

The term "women in development" came into use in the early 1970s, after the publication of Ester Boserup's *Women's Role in Economic Development* (1970). Boserup was the first to systematically delineate on a global level the sexual division of labour that existed in agrarian economies. She analysed the changes that occurred in traditional agricultural practices as societies became modernized and examined the differential impact of those changes on the work done by men and women. She concluded that in sparsely populated regions where shifting agriculture is practiced, women tend to do the majority of agricultural work (Buvinic, 1986).

METHODOLOGY

Survey research method was adopted for this study because the research study covers a large population and a complex study area. Simple random sampling method was used for the purposes of selecting study participants. The study area is Oron Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom state. Oron Federal Constituency consists of 5 local government areas which include; Oron, Mbo, Okobo, Udung Uko, and Urue Offong/Oruko local government areas. Oron Federal Constituency is part of Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State. The targeted population of this study was the female population in Oron Federal Constituency, which is also, refer to as Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District with Oron 130,259, Mbo 152,610, Udung Uko 105, 660, Okobo 153, 476, and Urue Offong/Oruko 79,253. The projected female population of Oron Federal Constituency, according to the Akwa Ibom State Demographic Dividend Profile (2018), as derived from the 2006 national population census (NPC, 2006) was 621,481. The projected female population of the constituency was 621,481 as at 2018.

In determining the sample size, the researcher used Alien Taro Yamane method. Yamane (1967) provides a simplified formula to calculate sample size. Therefore, the sample size of this study was 400, and was randomly selected from each of the local government area within Oron Federal Constituency. The headquarters of each of the local government areas were chosen by the researcher for the purpose of randomly selecting the study participants. A total of 393 (*n*) were finally adopted as sample size based on the retrieved questionnaire. Questionnaire was adopted as tool for data collection because it provided closed-ended options that were easy to choose by the participants. The data collected in this study were analysed descriptively using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULT

Level of Female Education in Oron Federal Constituency

Table 1: Distribution of primary school pupils for ECCDE class, by local government area and sex between 2009/2010 and 2014/2015 school sessions

Local Government Area	No. of Schools	ECCDE		
		M	F	MF
Mbo	29	3255	3910	7165
Okobo	33	3409	4000	7409
Oron	13	1376	1476	2852
UdungUko	11	917	1026	1943
UrueOffong/ Oruko	21	1065	1313	2378
Total	107	10,022	11,725	21,747

Source: Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development (2015).

Table 1 shows that in Oron Federal Constituency, Okobo Local Government Area has the highest number (7409) of pupils enrolled in Early Child Care Development Education (ECCDE) across the 33 primary schools, with females making the highest proportion of 4000 (54.1%) while the males are 3409 (45.9%). This is followed by Mbo Local Government Area with 3910 (54.6%) females and 3255 (45.4%) males, making a total of 7165 pupils across the 29 primary schools. Oron Local Government Area is next with 1476 (51.8%) females, while males are 1376 (48.2%), making a total of 2852 across 13 primary schools. This is followed by UrueOffong/ Oruko Local Government Area with a total of 2378 pupils, the females making the highest proportion with 1313 (55.2%), while the males are 1065 (44.8%) across 21 primary schools. UdungUko is the local government area with the least number of pupils and primary schools, with 1943 pupils at ECCDE class across 11 primary schools. This comprises 1026 (52.8%) of females, and 917 (47.2%) of males.

The analysis of Table 1 shows that Oron Federal Constituency as at 2014/2015 school session had a total of 21,747 pupils under Early Childhood Care and Development Education (ECCDE) across 107 primary schools. 11,725 (53.9%) were females, while males were 10,022 (46.1%). This implies that in ECCDE class at primary school level of education, females have the highest percentage of enrolment (11,725/53.9%) within 2014/2015 school year against (10,022/46.1%) males.

Roles of Educated Women in Community Development in Oron Federal Constituency**Table 2: Percentage Distribution of responses on Women Participation in Community Development in Oron Federal Constituency**

Women Participation in Community Development Programmes	Yes	%	No	%
Educational Intervention	342	85.5	58	14.5
Health Care intervention	357	89.3	43	10.7
Community Development Levy	368	92	32	8
Food Production/availability	353	88.3	47	11.7
Women Empowerment Intervention	374	93.5	26	6.5
Political Activities	279	69.8	121	30.2
Community Development Decision Making	213	53.3	187	46.7
Social Welfare intervention	308	77	92	23
Total	2594		606	

Source: Filed work (2023)

Table 2 shows that 342 (85.5%) agreed with “yes” against 58 (14.5%) with “No”, that women participate in community development through education intervention programmes in Oron Federal Constituency. 357 (89.3%) agreed against 43 (10.7%) that women participate in community development through health care intervention programmes/projects. 368 (92%) agreed that women participate in community development through contribution of community development levy, against 32 (8%). 353 (88.3%) said “Yes” that women participate in community development through production/availability of food against 47 (11.7%) who said “No”. 374 (93.5%) who said “Yes” that women participate in community development through women empowerment intervention programmes/projects, against 26 (6.5%) who disagreed. 279 (69.8%) agreed that women contribute to community development through political activities engagement against 121 (30.2%) who disagreed. 213 (53.3%) agreed that women contribute to community development through decision making at community level, against 187 (46.7%) who disagreed. 308 (77%) agreed that women participate in community development through social welfare intervention programmes/projects, against 92 (23%). This implies that the “Yes” are higher in proportion of responses than the “No” counterpart in all questions in this section.

Factors that affect women education in Oron Federal Constituency**Table 3: Percentage Distribution of Factors affecting women education in Oron Federal Constituency**

Factors that affect women education	Yes	%	No	%
Cultural belief	302	75.5	98	24.5
Poverty	353	88.3	47	11.7
Family roles	377	94.2	23	5.8
Early marriage	201	50.3	199	49.7
Gender role	278	69.5	122	30.5
Lack of sponsorship programmes for girl child education	317	79.3	83	20.7

Source: Field work (2023)

Table 3 shows responses on factors that affect women education in Oron Federal Constituency. Under cultural belief, those who say “Yes” have the highest proportion of responses with 302 (75.5%), while those who say “No” are 98 (24.5%). Under poverty, those who say “Yes” make the highest portion of respondents with 353 (88.3%), while those who say “No” are 47 (11.7%). Under family roles, those who say “Yes” are 377 (94.2%) which make the highest proportion of responses, while those who say “No” are 23 (5.8%). Under early marriage, those who say “Yes” make the highest portion of respondents with 201 (50.3%), while those who say “No” are 199 (49.7%). Under gender role as one of the factors that affect women education in Oron Federal Constituency, 278 (69.5%) of the respondents agree that gender role affects women quest for education, while 122 (30.5%) disagree. Under lack of sponsorship programmes for girl child education, 317 (79.3%) of the respondents say “Yes”, while those who say “No” are 83 (20.7%).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Emerging from the findings of the study is the fact that female education plays great roles in women participation in community development in Oron Federal Constituency. This was found to be supported by the discovery that education positioned women with required qualification and knowledge to contribute to the development of their respective communities within the local government areas in Oron Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom State. This finding supports the position of Somani (2017). According to Somani (2017), girls' education is pivotal to the development of society.

Findings further shows that throughout the 289 primary schools in Oron Federal Constituency, females are more enrolled than males. According to discovery through gathered information, Oron Federal Constituency people shows great belief in women education as girls

are found more in schools than boys. Emerging from the findings of the study is that educated women in Oron Federal Constituency play great roles in community development programmes/projects across the local government areas. It was gathered that educated women in Oron Federal Constituency engages in various community development programmes like; education intervention programmes, health care intervention, community levy, food production/availability, women empowerment intervention, political activities, decision making, and social welfare intervention programmes to bring about development in their different communities. This finding agrees with Alan (2010) who argues that; sustainable development of any country depends on the full and equal participation of women and men, education brings about empowerment, and in other words; education empowers women to engage in sustainable development activities.

Emergence from the findings of the study is the fact that there are factors that affect women education. According to gathered data, factors like cultural belief, poverty, family roles, early marriage, gender role and lack of sponsorship programmes for girl child education affect women quest for educational attainment in Oron Federal Constituency. British Council (2012) argued that many diverse socio-cultural factors influence the value that parents attach to their daughters' education. Gender norms and stereotypes exclude women and girls from decision-making, community participation and control over their own lives in many areas.

CONCLUSION

Education plays great role in empowering women to contribute to development, but the barriers of culture of exclusion driven by ideologies of patriarchy has brought about the slow pace in attaining development in many communities across the 5 local government areas in Oron Federal Constituency. Women education is on the rise in Oron Federal Constituency as more girl children are enrolled in 107 primary schools than the boys. Educated women in Oron Federal Constituency engaged various developmental programmes like health care intervention, educational intervention, social welfare empowerment and community development levy contribution, food production, and women empowerment. Various factors form barriers which the women in Oron Federal Constituency faced in their quest to contributing to the development of the constituency.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and analysis of data, the researcher proposed the following recommendations:

1. Cultural practice of women exclusion should be abolished from among the people of Oron Federal Constituency and Akwa Ibom State as a whole.
2. Government should see how to develop sponsorship programmes for girl child education.
3. Women should be given opportunities to take up leadership positions especially in rural communities in order to have opportunities to contribute their wisdom toward community development.
4. Women should be allowed to be part of decision making bodies on issues that affect them.

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